

Original Research

Training and Development Programs in Public, Private, and Foreign Commercial Banks in Bangladesh: an Empirical Inquiry

Md. Mizanur Rahman Chowdhury and Zahurul Alam
Department of Management, University of Chittagong, Chittagong,
Bangladesh

Mohammad Aktaruzzaman Khan¹
Department of Business Administration, International Islamic University
Chittagong, Chittagong, Bangladesh

Abstract

Training and development activity is indispensable for the survival of any type of organization especially service-oriented organization where the skills of the workforce should be continuously upgraded for the survival of the cut-throat competition. Unfortunately, this function is not given equal emphasis in the banking sector. The present study attempts to discover any statistically significant perceptual differences among public, private, and foreign banks regarding development and training programs in the selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. The study reveals that there are statistically significant perceptual differences among public, private, and foreign bank employees regarding different contents of training and development programs in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. The study further investigated that selected foreign bankers' perception of various components of training and development programs is better in comparison to the perception of public and private bankers of Bangladesh. Finally, the study finding implies that private and public banks should put greater emphasis on their training and development programs.

Keywords: Training and development, Cut throat competition, Skills up-gradation.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: rajarkul2002@yahoo.com

Introduction

Training becomes important the moment an organization realizes the need for improvement and growth in the job. But most of the times, organizations commence on job enlargement and enrichment to promote employees' confidence, motivation and satisfaction when in the fact the original problem with work performance lies in sufficiency development. Training is one of the most inevitable and dependable Human Resource Development methods to increase organizational and employee productivity (Bhatti & Kaur, 2009). Training should be developed in such a way that they create a win-win situation for both organization and employees may attain their goals if learning skills are shifted successfully to the workplace (Kauffeld & Lehmann-Willenbrock, 2010). HRD is indispensable in sustaining effective performance and achievement of firm's objectives by introducing training. Training certifies an adequate supply of employees that are technically proficient for management jobs (Mullins, 2007). Trainings conducted at the right time provide big rewards for increased productivity, knowledge, allegiance and benefaction.

Hence, modern employee has to grasp throughout their lives because of enduring changes in requirements for professional proficiency. The trend in business education world concerns with the implementation of creating and problem-based approaches in executive training (Minina & Nikitina, 2012). Training concentrates on the development of logical thinking, the capacity of profound vision of every day routines and apparently simple events (Bordovskaya & Rean, 2004). The central issue on training is to engage employee in effective learning to the maximum utility of training (Nikandrou et al, 2008). Employees value continuous learning as concern for employability, which is linked to demands of knowledge economy (Kuijpers & Scheerens, 2006). Proper training program design and delivery is a major contributor to the transfer of learning that meets the needs of the learner and organization (Montesino, 2002). Program design should therefore include a needs assessment, clear program goals that align training with strategic direction of the organization (Khan & Ali, 2015). A properly designed program has greater success in transferring learning to workplace (Colquitt, LePine, & Noe, 2000). Trainees with a high degree of self-efficacy tend to be more motivated learners and can accomplish more (Chiaburu & Marinova, 2005). Assessing individual performance and providing feedback prior to training can also have a positive impact on motivation.

In doing so, supervisors play a key role in post-training by giving feedback (Kraiger et al., 2004). Career development is a lifelong series of activities (workshops) that contribute to a person's career exploitation, establishment, success and fulfilment. Many employers today have strengthened career focus of their HRD activities. The focus is no longer just, how best can you serve our company. The reality is that, most people will have to change employers several times during their work lives especially among Y-generation. Career development involves concerted efforts directed towards assessing employees' potentials identifying likely career paths for them and designing and implementing various forms of training and experience to prepare that person for job advanced. Career management is a process for enabling employees to develop their career skills and interest and to use these skills and interests most effectively both within the firm and after they leave (Armstrong, 2005).

Problem Statement

In order to address the above issue, there is insignificant number of studies, has so far been made in Bangladesh regarding comparative study among public, private and foreign bank employees concerning different contents of Training program in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. The development of overall skills of the employees, reduction of stress level, development technical skills, need-based training programs, helpful in the long run, and quality of the instructor are vital elements for the efficacy of the employee training in public banks of Bangladesh (Islam, Mridha, Sharna, Rahman, Mosharraf, & Nower, 2019). A study by Zahidul explored the level of proficiency of training among different commercial banks in Bangladesh. But the author didn't throw light on the comparative picture of Public, Private and Foreign banker's perception regarding different contents of training program (Islam, 2015). Another study on selected business enterprises found job training and job orientation are the two most frequently used training method; among the training courses offered by selected enterprises (Quadir, Azad, & Uddin, 2006). Absar, Sikder, and Hossain (2010) also made a study for exploring the differences between the public and private sector enterprises of Bangladesh, which shown that overall status of training and development practices of private sector industrial enterprises is significantly better than that of public sector industrial enterprises (Absar, & Mahmood, 2011; Khan, Hoque, & Shahabuddin, 2019).

But no attempt has been made to explore the differences among public, private and foreign bank employees regarding Development and Training program in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. If the perceptions of Bank employee's regarding Training and Development doesn't consider dully, an organization does not achieve objectives training and development program's objectives. Non-fulfilment of an organization's training and development objectives results in low productivity of organization's workforce, highest wastages of monetary investment which have a greater opportunity cost, highest rate of absenteeism and turnover, Low employee morale. Ultimately, an organization will lose its competitive advantages in the long run.

Individual as well as organisational performances are vitally affected by training. Most of the literature available reports the different aspects of employees training. However, little matter exists on this subject with respect to the perceptions of employees with respect to different contents of training programs in the banking sector and this study aims to fill in this gap.

Review of Literature

Training and development are important components of HRM (Tahir, Yousafzai, Jan, & Hashim, 2014). Thus, it is vital for organization confirming the presence of skilled and capable employees for improved performance and employees will be than eligible when they have the knowledge and skill of performing the task. Training and development would provide opportunities to the employees to make a better career life and get better job position in organization. In doing so, organization's proficiency would be increased. On the other hand, workforces are the resources and blessings of an organization if they are capable and educated would perform better than those who are incapable and untrained.

Employees are conscious of the objectives of training in the organization, the training objectives are clear to them before the training and the selection standard (Ampomah, 2016). Ampomah's study also explored that employee are motivated through training; and training and development results into better performance. The study approved that training and development of all staff should be thoroughly pursued and made obligatory. Training in organizations holds the key to open the potential growth and development opportunities to achieve a competitive margin (Rama & Shaik, 2012). Organizations train and develop their human force to the full extent in order to enhance their productive capacity. Thus, knowledge, skill and capabilities are determinants of employees' performance which organizations need to continuously invest in wisely in order to improve their employees' productivity. As supported by Noe and Peacock (Noe & Peacock, 2008), organizations spend a mentionable amount of money and time on training to aid employee's learning of job-related competencies. Thus, it is important to completely provide the outcomes from training efforts (Dowling, 2004).

Functions of Human resource development (HRD) can be utilized to ensure that organization workforce can successfully confirm their challenges and threats (Werner & DeSimone, 2009) of rapid and non-stop changes. According to Casse and Banahan (2007), the different methods to training and development need to be explored. It has come to their notice by their own preferred model and through large organization's experience. According to Davenport (2006), it is easy to implement strategy with the internet supported software. There is documented evidence that training activities have a positive impact on the performance of individuals and teams. Training activities can also be beneficial regarding other outcomes at both the individual and team level such as attitudes, motivation, and empowerment (Aguinis & Kraiger, 2009). Training as an essential element to an employee for the development of the companies because some of the employees have lack of knowledge skills and competencies and failed to accomplish task on timely basis (Abbas, 2014). Training is important mean to improve the organization performance and effectiveness (Singh & Mohanty, 2012). Trainer makes an effort in achieving training as well as organizational objectives (Mahbuba, 2013).

There is less wastage of time, money and resources if employees are properly trained (Ahmad, Khan, Abdullah, & Rashid, 2017; James, Kumar, Tayal, Chauhan, Wadhawa, & Panchal, 2022). Intangible assets are equally as valuable as financial and physical assets but they are not something that can be touched and they are nonmonetary. Intangible assets have been shown to be responsible for a company's competitive advantage. A study by the American Society for Training and Development of more than 500 publicly traded U.S.-based companies found that companies that invested the most in training and development had a shareholder return that was 86 percent higher than companies in the bottom half and 46 percent higher than the market average. Training and development have a direct influence on human and social capital because they affect education, work-related know-how and competence, and work-life relationships (Uddin, Ali, & Khan, 2020, 2021). Training and development can have an indirect influence on customer satisfaction (Khan & Ali, 2012; Khan, Toy, & Siddique, 2010; Uddin, Ali, & Khan, 2018) and social capital by helping employee's better serve customers by providing them with the knowledge needed to create patents and intellectual property. Intangible assets also contribute to a company's competitive advantage because they are difficult to duplicate.

In view of the above review of literatures, the study intends to explore the differences among public, private and foreign bank employees regarding training and development programs in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. In doing so, the authors also null-hypothesized that there is no statistically significant difference among public, private and foreign bank employees regarding HRD activities of development and training program.

Rationale

So far, no significant study was conducted to explore the differences among public, private and foreign bank employees regarding training and development program in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. Whereas, this is one of the important functions of HRD activity (Uddin, Khan, & Mohammad, 2015; Uddin, Khan, & Farhana, 2014). According to Agrawal (2005), HRD covers the following functions to survive, grow and sustain in the complete financial market. (i) Performance and potential appraisal, (ii) Employees career planning and development. (iii) Development and training programmes. (iv) Organization development. (v) Recognizing and rewarding the contribution (honours and awards) (vi) Employees welfare and quality of work life. (vii) Taking steps for controlling stress. (viii) Planning overall development of the bank and analyzing changing pattern of employees. (ix) Developing Team Spirit. (x) Rendering quality and satisfactory services (quality management). Hoque (1994) investigated 10 industrial enterprises (5 public and 5 private). He found that human resource development (HRD) had positive impact on organizational effectiveness (OE). Ather and Solaiman (1995) assessed human resource development (HRD) practices of 50 public and private industrial enterprises. They found that training needs of the employees of the sample enterprises were identified on the basis of circumstances, corporate objective, new recruitment, introduction of new technology, new assignment by promotion, existing requirement for skill development and improving productivity, requirement for filling present and future vacancies, trend of profit or loss, and comparative study on productivity and output. Khan and Jahur (2007) examined the HRD practices of 38 industrial enterprises of Bangladesh. The study found that the surveyed organizations' HRD programs were not up to date which is in line with stands of research findings (Chowdhury, Othman, Khan, & Sulaiman, 2020; Jahur, Quadir, & Khan, 2014; Khan & Ali, 2014, 2015; Khan, Islam, & Ali, 2014; Khan, Ali, & Arefeen, 2014; Rahman & Khan, 2008). Employee training and development has enormous impact on organizational effectiveness. It is observed that more investment in training and development has led to more profitability of the private sector industrial enterprises of Bangladesh (Hoque, 1994). Ahsan, Abdullah, Fie, and Alam (2009) have studied the effect of training and development, team work, compensation, HR planning, performance appraisal and employee security on business performance. Regression results showed that four variables training and development, team work, HR planning and performance appraisal have positive and significant influence on business performance of Bangladeshi organizations. Quadir et al., (2006) in their study found that in the selected business enterprises, job training and job orientation are the two most frequently used training method; among the training courses offered by selected enterprises. Absar, Sikder, and Hossain (2010) made a study for exploring the differences between the public and private sector enterprises of Bangladesh, which show that overall status of training and development practices of private sector industrial enterprises is significantly better than

that of public sector industrial enterprises (Uddin & Khan, 2017; Uddin, Khan, & Solaiman, 2014; Uddin, Khan, Uddin, & Solaiman, 2015). The study conducted by Kabir, Ullah, & Chowdhury (2013) mainly aimed at finding the relationship between training and productivity as well as to observe the effect of training cost on profitability. The results revealed that the productivity growth after training is significant and shows a positive impact of training cost on profitability. As the previous study did not highlight the responses of Bank Employees towards various Activities of Human Resource Development among selected public, private and foreign banks, the present study attempts to discover the issue.

Methodology

Research Hypothesis

The null hypothesis is that there are no significant differences among public, private and foreign bank employee's perception regarding 'Development and Training program' in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh.

Population and Sampling

There are 56 commercial banks operating in Bangladesh. Banks that were started their journey before 1991 is considered as first-generation banks which are 16 in numbers. Second generation banks started their business in between 1991 to 1999 which is 8 in numbers. There are 8 banks which started their operations from 1999 to 2010, are considered as third generation banks. There are 9 banks which started their venture from the year 2011 to the present year which is considered as fourth generation banks. Besides the local banks, there are also 10 foreign banks operating in our country.

On the basis of 25 years banking experience, $N_0=36$ commercial banks (sample frame). A 95% level of confidence and 5% level of precision ($e=.05$), the sample size for the study by using formulae given by Yamane (1967:886) is 32 Banks. These 32 banks have been selected randomly from 36 banks according to the number of public, private and foreign banks. (According to proportion 5 public, 24 private and 3 foreign banks are selected). Out of 32 banks—5 branches of each banks are selected purposively by the method of Purposive sampling. 2 executives from each bank are selected on the basis of their 5 years banking experience. $32*5(2 \text{ respondent from each branch}) = 320$ respondents. The number and method of sampling techniques of respondents selected are in line with the social science research conducted earlier in Bangladesh (Khan & Ali, 2014, 2015). After sorting the responses, 236 respondents were considered valid and the remaining responses are left out because of incomplete and inconsistent responses. I have collected data from different banking branches of different cities operating in Bangladesh. To ensure representativeness, 175 private banks branch, 55 public banks branch and 6 foreign banks branch are considered for the study.

Data Analysis

The response rate was 80%. The study applied Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in order to examine the differences among public, private and foreign bank employee's

perception regarding ‘Development and Training program’ in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh through SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 17. Responses were taken by five-point Likert Scale (Strongly agree=1, agree= 2, Neutral=3, Disagree=4, strongly disagree =5).

Analysis and Findings of The Study

Table 1. Working Areas

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Investment, credit and loan	43	18.2	18.2	18.2
	Foreign Exchange	23	9.7	9.7	28.0
	Deposit	2	.8	.8	28.8
	General Banking	73	30.9	30.9	59.7
	Manager	11	4.7	4.7	64.4
	others	84	35.6	35.6	100.0
	Total	236	100.0	100.0	

Table 2. Types of Banks

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	private	175	74.2	74.2	74.2
	public	55	23.3	23.3	97.5
	foreign	6	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	236	100.0	100.0	

Table 3. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.843	.854	17

Table 4. Length of Service

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	less than one	4	1.7	1.7	1.7
	1-5	119	50.4	50.4	52.1
	6-10	80	33.9	33.9	86.0
	more than 10	33	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	236	100.0	100.0	

5.1 Testing Hypothesis of finding out significant perceptual differences among the public, private and foreign banker's regarding training and development program:

The objective of the study is to test the null hypothesis of significant differences among the selected public, private and foreign bank employee's perception regarding 'Training and development program' in some selected banking enterprises in Bangladesh. By conducting ANOVA analysis, the following results were obtained:

Table 5. ANOVA Analysis

Development and Training program					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.462	2	1.731	3.951	.021
Within Groups	102.080	233	.438		
Total	105.542	235			

Source: Authors' calculation by using SPSS-20, 2020.

The above ANOVA analysis represents that $p < .05$, so Null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of "statistically no significant difference among public, private and foreign bank employee's perception regarding HRD activities of 'Development and Training program'" is rejected. So, there is a statistically significant difference among public, private and foreign bank employee's perception regarding HRD activities of 'Development and Training program'.

5.2 Different perception of public, private and foreign banker's regarding their training and development program:

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min.	Max.
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
					Private	175		
Public	55	1.8000	.89028	.12004	1.5593	2.0407	1.00	4.00
Foreign	6	1.0000	.00000	.00000	1.0000	1.0000	1.00	1.00
Total	236	1.7203	.67016	.04362	1.6344	1.8063	1.00	4.00

Source: Authors' calculation by using SPSS-20, 2020.

The above table represents that the bankers of the selected foreign banks perceive that their organization conduct 'Development and Training program' in a better way in comparison to public and private banks in Bangladesh.

5.3 Testing hypothesis of finding out significant perceptual differences among the public, private and foreign banker's regarding different components of training need assessment:

Table 7. ANOVA

Components of Training Need Assessment		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Difference of Sig.
Department doesn't meet goals of the organization, need training.	Between Groups	4.455	2	2.227	2.585	.078	
	Within Groups	200.778	233	.862			yes
	Total	205.233	235				
budget & facilities	Between Groups	5.092	2	2.546	2.746	.066	yes
	Within Groups	216.073	233	.927			
	Total	221.165	235				
Legal, Social, Political and Economic issues are considered	Between Groups	4.866	2	2.433	2.889	.058	
	Within Groups	196.236	233	.842			yes
	Total	201.102	235				
Reward for appropriate learned behaviour	Between Groups	6.217	2	3.109	3.140	.045	
	Within Groups	230.664	233	.990			yes
	Total	236.881	235				
HRD/training be emphasized where objectives are not met and performance problems exist and this type of organizational analysis are performed by for training need assessment	Between Groups	9.243	2	4.622	4.054	.019	
	Within Groups	265.651	233	1.140			Very sig.
	Total	274.894	235				
Training to fill retirement, turnover and age gap	Between Groups	3.529	2	1.764	3.511	.031	
	Within Groups	117.098	233	.503			yes
	Total	120.627	235				
New or changed equipment considered for training	Between Groups	5.875	2	2.937	2.981	.053	
	Within Groups	229.562	233	.985			yes
	Total	235.436	235				

Source: Authors' calculation by using SPSS-20, 2020

5.4 Measures of Central Tendencies and Standard Deviation regarding different contents of Training Needs Assessment:

Table 8. Contents of TNA (Training needs assessment)

Contents of TNA	Public		Private		Foreign	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Department doesn't meet goals of the organization, need training.	2.0545	1.09575	2.3371	Std. Dev.	1.8333	.40825
Amount of budget & facilities for budget is considered.	2.1091	Std. Dev.	2.2343	.96904	1.3333	.51640
Legal, Social, Political and Economic issues are considered.	2.2286	.93113	1.9091	.90825	1.8333	.40825
Reward for appropriate learned behaviour.	2.0545	.98917	2.4343	1.00857	2.1667	.40825
HRD or training emphasis	2.8727	1.34790	2.4229	.97882	2.1667	.40825
Training to fill retirement, turnover and age gap	2.1273	1.00101	2.3886	.93948	1.8333	.75277
New or changed equipment considered for training.	2.2000	1.11222	2.4571	.96320	1.6667	.51640

Source: Authors' calculation by using SPSS-20, 2020

Discussion and conclusions

In this article, we investigated the effectiveness of training programs in public, private and foreign commercial banks operating in Bangladesh. The study demonstrated that bankers of selected foreign banks almost strongly agreed that their organizations-initiated training/HRD interventions in that area where their organization didn't meet their goals. The study also expressed that foreign banker nearly strongly agreed that available budget, facilities for providing training, materials on hand and the expertise for giving training within the organizations was considered for training need assessment, which is better in comparison to the selected Public and Private Banker's judgement regarding the statement. The study also explored that Foreign and Public banker typically strongly agreed that Legal compliances issues (such as safety training, fire training), Social issues (such as use of Internet, face book in office time etc.), Economic issues (such as motivating the employees when the company falls in economic crisis etc), Political issues (how to handle the different stakeholders of the state such as political parties, Law enforcing agencies etc.) , were considered in conducting the training need analysis which is better in comparison to Private Bankers judgement regarding the issues.

The study further represented that Foreign and Public banker almost agreed that trainee was rewarded on the job for the appropriate learned behaviour acquired through training

which is better in comparison to Private Banker's judgement regarding the statement. Private Banker's judgement regarding the statement was approximately neutral. Their banker's thought that their organization was conducting their training program for exploring opportunities for improvement and problem identification but not in a better way as like as Foreign and Private Banks. The study also revealed that Foreign and Private Banker's nearly agreed that HRD or training emphasis should be placed in that department where objectives were not met and performance problems existed. The study further scrutinized that foreign banker roughly agreed that training was needed to fill up the gap caused by retirement, turnover, age etc. for training need assessment, which is better in comparison to Public and Private Bankers judgement regarding the statement. Public and Private Banker thought in a different way. The study reviewed that foreign banker roughly agreed that grievances, absenteeism, turnover, accidents, observation of employee behaviour, attitude survey of employees, customer complain etc. were considered for conducting training, which is better in comparison to Public and Private Bankers judgement regarding the elements of training. The study expressed that foreign banker practically agreed that new or changed equipment presented HRD or training problems which is better in comparison to Public and Private Bankers Judgement regarding the statement. The study represented that Foreign and Public banker substantially agreed that one of the most common techniques of HRD/training needs determination was management request or management interrogation, which is better in comparison to Private Banker's mentality regarding the topics.

The study explored that foreign bankers absolutely agreed that one of the most common techniques of HRD/training needs determination was exit interviews which is better in comparison to Public and Private Bankers mentality regarding the statement. The study further examined that Public, Private and foreign bankers virtually agreed various levels or participating units in the organization had been involved with developing the training program, initiated with the evaluation of the wanted end results of training. It is to note that the perceptions of selected foreign bankers towards various components of Training and Development program is better compare to the perception of Public and Private Bankers in Bangladesh. Therefore, the authorities of Public and Private Banks should consider the stated contents of Training and Development program passionately and productively as like as foreign banks so that perception of their employees are positively changed towards their various contents of Training and Development program. The ultimate outcome of conducting various contents of Training and Development program passionately and productively is that Productivity of the employees are positively changed which provides a competitive advantage to the organization.

Foreign bankers perceive that their organization conduct 'development and training program' in better ways than public and private banks. Hence, in order to make the programs successful and face the challenges of global competition, public and private sector banks should emphasize their existing development and training program (Khan & Ali, 2014, 2015)

As a final methodological note, we want to emphasize that the analysis presented in this article is primarily based on observed associations and relationships, using descriptive/nonparametric testing procedures. An important question remains how much the observed relationships actually tell us about underlying causal relationships and in

which direction these causal relationships act. We believe that a more extended deterministic model is needed to further test these underlying causal relationships and their direction in future research in this domain. The current study covered only selected sample banks. A wider number of banks in leading cities and in different sectors such as health, transportation, and tourism can also be taken into consideration in the future enquiry.

References

- Abbas, Z. (2014). Identification of factors and their impact on employees' training and organizational performance in Pakistan. *Kasbit Journal of Management & Social Science*, 7(1), 93-109.
- Absar, M.M.N., & Mahmood, M. (2011). New HRM Practices in the Public and Private Sector Industrial Enterprises of Bangladesh: A Comparative Assessment. *International Review of Business Research Papers* 7(2), 118-136.
- Absar, M.M.N., Sikder, Z.H., & Hossain, M.J. (2010). Training and development practices in industrial enterprises of Bangladesh: A comparative study between the public and private sector. *Dhaka University Journal of Management*, 2(1), 25-38.
- Agrawal, V. H. (2005). *A study of the impact of HRD practices and measures to resolve pertinent challenging issues of HRD in commercial banks in India*. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation: Saurashtra University, India.
- Aguinis, H., & Kraiger, K. (2009). Benefits of training and development for individuals and teams, organizations, and society. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 60, 451-474.
- Ahmad, A., Khan, M.A., Abdullah, A.A.M., & Rashid, M. H. U. (2017). Environmental disclosures: A study on some selected pharmaceutical and chemical companies in Bangladesh. *IIUC Business Review*, 6, 9-24.
- Ahsan, N., Abdullah, Z., Fie, D. Y. G., & Alam, S. S. (2009). A study of job stress on job satisfaction among university staff in Malaysia: Empirical study. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 121-131.
- Ampomah, P. (2016). The Effect of Training and Development on Employee Performance in a Private Tertiary Institution in Ghana. Case Study: Pentecost University College (Puc)-Ghana). *Asian Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 3(1), 29-33.
- Armstrong, M. (2005). *Human resource management practices* (9th Ed). London: Kogan Page.
- Ather, S., & Solaiman, M. (1995). Human resource development practices in Bangladesh - A study on some selected firms in Chittagong. *Chittagong University Studies*, 11(1), 19-37.

- Bhatti, M.A., & Kaur, S. (2009). Factors effecting transfer of training: a fresh review. Paper presented at the 12th International Business Information Management Conference.
- Bordovskaya, N., & Rean, A. (2004). Pedagogics. Available at: www.gumer.info/bibliotek_Buks/Pedagog/Bordo/04.php
- Casse & Banahan (2007). Impact of training and development on the employee performance: A case study from different Banking sectors of North Panjab. *The Russian Federation Publication*.
- Chiaburu, D. S., & Marinova, S. V. (2005). What predicts skill transfer? An exploratory study of goal orientation, training self- efficacy and organizational supports. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 9(2), 110-123.
- Chowdhury, M. M. I., Othman, K. B., Khan, M. A., Sulaiman, I. F. (2020). Role of effective corporate governance and motivational leadership in increasing productivity and efficiency of human resources. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 20(10), 29-39.
- Colquitt, J. A., LePine, J. A., & Noe, R. A. (2000). Toward an integrative theory of training motivation: a meta-analytic path analysis of 20 years of research. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(5), 678.
- Davenport, T. H. (2006). Competing on analytics. *Harvard Business Review*, 84(1), 98.
- Dowling, P. (2004). *International human resource management: managing people in a multinational environment* (4th Ed). London: Thomson Learning.
- Hoque, M. J. (1994). Human resource development and organizational effectiveness. In R. B. Talukder (Eds.), *Management of Change in South Asia*. Dhaka: UPL, 433-451.
- Islam, M. Z. (2015). Efficiency of training: a comparative study on some selected commercial banks in Bangladesh. *Journal of Asian Business Strategy*, 5(6), 116-124.
- Islam, N., Mridha, E. M., Sharna, J. S., Rahman, M. D., Mosharraf, M., & Nower, N. (2019). An evaluation of the effectiveness of employee training in the government banks of Bangladesh. In 10th International Conference on "Developing Organizations for the Future: Re-Interpreting the Modern Business Landscape" at: ICFAI Business School, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.
- Jahur, M. S., Quadir, S. M. N., & Khan, M. A. (2014). Determinants of stock market performance in Bangladesh. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 13(1), 16-28.
- James, A. T., Kumar, G., Tayal, P., Chauhan, A., Wadhawa, C., & Panchal, J. (2022). Analysis of human resource management challenges in implementation of

- industry 4.0 in Indian automobile industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 176, 121483.
- Kabir, M. R., Ullah, M. M., & Chowdhury, M. M. (2013). Impact of Human Resources Training on the Performances of Banks-An Empirical Study. *China-USA Business Review*, 12(5), 524-531.
- Kauffeld, S., & Lehmann- Willenbrock, N. (2010). Sales training: effects of spaced practice on training transfer. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 34(1), 23-37.
- Khan, M. A., & Ali, A. J. (2012). Factors affecting customers' intention towards online shopping in Bangladesh. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 11(1), 21-36.
- Khan, M. A., & Ali, A. J. (2014). The role of training in reducing poverty: the case of the ultra-poor in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 18(4), 272-281. DOI: 10.1111/ijtd.12041
- Khan, M. A., & Ali, A. J. (2015). Do non-governmental organisations' socio-economic and training programmes improve disaster prevention capacity of their beneficiaries? *International Social Work*, 58(3), 401-420. DOI: 10.1177/0020872815570074
- Khan, M. A., & Jahur, M. S. (2007). Human resource development practices in some selected business enterprises in Bangladesh: An explanatory study. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 6(1), 16-32.
- Khan, M. A., Ali, A. J., & Arefeen, S. (2014). The impact of training on NGO beneficiaries' education in Bangladesh: The missing link. *Advances in Environmental Biology*, 8(9), 679-88.
- Khan, M. A., Islam, M. A., & Ali, A. J. (2014). Educational development of NGO beneficiaries in Bangladesh: a disjunction between programmes and implementation. *Asian Social Science*, 10(22), 57-69.
- Khan, M.A., Hoque, N., Shahabuddin, A. M. (2019). HRM practices and performance management in public service organizations in Bangladesh: An empirical study. *IIUC Studies*, 16, 9-34.
- Khan, M. A., Toy, M. M., & Siddique, A. (2010). Stimulating factors and justification of the strategic approach applicable for the internationalisation of SMEs in Bangladesh. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 9(2), 1-14.
- Kraiger, et al. (2004). Collaborative planning for training impact. *Human Resource Management*, 43(4), 337-351.
- Kuijpers, M. A. C. T., & Scheerens, J. (2006). Career competencies for the modern career. *Journal of Career Development*, 32, 303-319.

- Mahbuba, S. (2013). Impact of training in pharmaceutical industry: An assessment on Square Pharmaceuticals Limited, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 2(2), 576-587.
- Minina, V., & Nikitina, I. (2012). Intellectual competition as technology for professional training of managers: GSOM experience. *Journal of Management Development*, 31(3), 263-274.
- Montesino, M. U. (2002). Strategic alignment of training, transfer- enhancing behaviors, and training usage: A posttraining study. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 13(1), 89-108.
- Mullins, L. J. (2007). *Management and organizational behavior* (8th ed.). London: Prentice Hall.
- Nikandrou, I., Apospori, E., Panayotopoulou, L., Stavrou, E. T., & Papalexandris, N. (2008). Training and firm performance in Europe: the impact of national and organizational characteristics. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19(11), 2057-2078.
- Noe, R. A., & Peacock, M. (2008). *Employee training and development*. New York: McGrawHill, Inc.
- Quadir, S. M., Azad, A. S. M., & Uddin, S. M. (2006). Human resource development practices in Bangladesh: a study of selected business enterprises. *Bangladesh Journal of Resources and Development*, 3(1), 45-59.
- Rahman, M. O., & Khan, M. A. (2008). Display unit for Bangla characters. *IIUC Studies*, 4, 71-86.
- Rama Devi, V., & Shaik, N. (2012). Training & development-a jump starter for employee performance and organizational effectiveness. *International Journal of Social Science & Interdisciplinary Research*, 1(7), 202-207.
- Singh, R., & Mohanty, M. (2012). Impact of training practices on employee productivity: A comparative study. *Interscience Management Review*, 2(2), 87-92.
- Tahir, N., Yousafzai, I. K., Jan, S., & Hashim, M. (2014). The impact of training and development on employees performance and productivity a case study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(4), 86-98.
- Uddin, M. M., & Khan, M. A. (2017). Role of leadership on organizational learning at private universities of Bangladesh. *IIUC Studies*, 14(2), 9-34.
- Uddin, M. M., & Khan, M. A., & Mohammad, K. D. (2015). Interest-free banking in Bangladesh: a study on customers' perception of uses and awareness. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 1-16.

- Uddin, M. M., Khan, M. A., & Farhana, N. (2014). Banking services and customer perception in some selected commercial banks in Bangladesh. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 13(1), 1-15.
- Uddin, M. S., Khan, M. A., & Solaiman, M. (2014). Human resource development through training on business teachers in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, 4(1), 83-96.
- Uddin, M. S., Khan, M. A., Uddin, M. K., & Solaiman, M. (2015). University-Industry Collaboration (UIC) for developing highly skilled and productive business graduates in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Management and Business Research*, 5(1), 31-41.
- Uddin, M., Ali, K., & Khan, M. A. (2018). Impact of service quality (SQ) on student satisfaction: empirical evidence in the higher education context of emerging economy. *AL- 'ABQARI: Journal of Islamic Social Sciences and Humanities*, 16, 31-67.
- Uddin, M., Ali, K., & Khan, M. A. (2020). Perceived social support (PSS) and work-life balance in a developing country: The moderating impact of work-life policy. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 13(4), 733-761.
- Uddin, M., Ali, K., & Khan, M. A. (2021). Supervisory and co-worker support on the work-life balance of working women in the banking sector: a developing country perspective. *Journal of Family Studies*, 1-21.
- Werner, J. M., & DeSimone, R. L. (2009). Evaluating HRD programs. *Human Resource Development*, 5.

<p>COPYRIGHTS</p> <p>©2022 The author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE</p> <p>Chowdhury, M., Alam, Z., & Khan, M. (2022). Training and Development Programs in Public, Private, and Foreign Commercial Banks in Bangladesh: an Empirical Inquiry. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 9(9), 550-565.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7179888</p> <p>URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_158729.html</p>	